

Phenylhydrazine Sulphinic Acid—A New Gravimetric Reagent for Tellurium

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Phenylhydrazine sulphinic acid, a new analytical reagent has been employed for the gravimetric determination of tellurium in presence of several metals. The reagent precipitates tellurium quantitatively from strong hydrochloric acid solutions ranging from 25 to 75% by volume. 5 to 100 mg of the element can be estimated rapidly by this procedure.

WELL known reagents for the determination of tellurium by reduction are hydrazine hydrochloride and sulphurous acid in hydrochloric acid¹. However, no systematic studies have been reported on the determination of tellurium using phenylhydrazine sulphinic acid. The reagent precipitates tellurium quantitatively from solutions of hydrochloric acid that are stronger than 3.0N (approximately 25% by volume). 5 to 100 mg. of the element can be determined with accuracy. Phenylhydrazine sulphinic acid is easily obtained by the action of sulphur dioxide on an ethereal solution of phenylhydrazine².

Experimental

All the chemicals used were AnalaR BDH grade.

Tellurium solution: A solution of telluric acid containing about 3.5 g per litre was prepared and standardised¹.

Phenylhydrazine Sulphinic acid: The reagent is prepared by the action of sulphur dioxide on an ethereal solution of phenylhydrazine. It forms white shining crystals, freely soluble in water, alcohol and acetone, yield, 80%. On gentle heating phenylhydrazine sulphinic acid loses a molecule of water forming sulphur yellow thionyl phenylhydrazine².

Reagent solution: An aqueous solution of the reagent (1% w/v) was prepared.

Recommended procedure: An aliquot (25 ml) of the standard tellurium solution containing 50 mg of the element was received in a 400 ml beaker. About 30 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid followed by 10 ml of the reagent solution were added and the solution diluted to 100 ml. The contents were heated on a hot plate for 10 to 15 minutes. The granular elementary tellurium separates out completely. It was then filtered through a G-4 crucible, washed with hot water, followed by alcohol and

dried at 110° to constant weight. The results of 10 estimations are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF TELLURIUM AND ITS SEPARATION FROM DIVERSE IONS

Amount of tellurium taken (mg.)	Foreign ion added (mg.)	Amount of tellurium found (mg.)	Error %
4.97	—	4.96	-0.201
9.95	—	9.97	+0.201
14.92	—	14.92	+0.201
19.90	—	19.87	-0.150
24.87	—	24.85	-0.080
29.85	—	29.87	+0.060
34.82	—	34.79	-0.100
39.80	—	39.83	+0.070
49.75	—	49.79	+0.080
99.50	—	99.46	-0.040
49.75	Cu ²⁺ (40)	49.72	-0.063
49.75	Cd ²⁺ (25)	49.78	+0.080
49.75	Cr ³⁺ (20)	49.80	+0.100
49.75	Ni ²⁺ (40)	49.69	-0.120
49.75	Ca ²⁺ (25)	49.73	-0.040
49.75	Mg ²⁺ (25)	49.71	-0.080
49.75	Sr ²⁺ (25)	49.79	+0.080
49.75	Fe ³⁺ (30)	49.79	+0.080
49.75	Fe ³⁺ (30)	49.70	-0.100
49.75	Zn ²⁺ (25)	49.72	-0.063
49.75	Th ⁴⁺ (10)	49.72	-0.063
49.75	UO ₂ ²⁺ (10)	49.79	+0.080
49.75	Sb ³⁺ (20)	49.80	+0.100
49.75	Phosphate (40)	49.73	-0.080
49.75	Acetate (50)	49.78	+0.063
49.75	Sulphate (100)	49.72	-0.063
49.75	Nitrate (25)	49.72	-0.063

Results and Discussion

Acidity and Reagent concentration: The acidity of the solution should be maintained between 3.0N to 9.0N (approximately 25 to 75% by volume) for complete precipitation of tellurium. The reagent is added in the form of a 1% solution in water and 1 ml of this solution is usually sufficient for the precipitation of 5 mg of the metal. Excess of the reagent causes no harm to the determination.

Diverse ions: The procedure separates tellurium from copper, nickel, iron, zinc, cobalt and aluminium. Separation can also be achieved from anions such as phosphate, acetate, nitrate and sulphate when present as their sodium salts. Selenium interferes with the

determination and must be absent. The results are summarised in Table 1.

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References

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